

Studies on the compositions of nutmeg and mace (*Myristica fragrans* Houtt.) from Tellicherry and Kannur region, Kerala

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Abstract : Studies on the fruits of the nutmeg tree, *Myristica fragrans* Houtt. (family : Myristicaceae) were carried out for the two different parts of the fruit, that is nutmeg and mace collected from Tellicherry and Kannur area (Kerala). The dried material was studied using HPLC and other laboratory techniques. The major compounds identified were carbohydrate, starch, reducing sugars, protein, phenol, fat and fatty acids and minerals like K, Ca, Fe, Cu, Zn and Mn. Essential oils were also identified. The chemical composition obtained was compared with the information already available in literature for other parts of the country. The results obtained are promising due to the quality and quantity of the various chemical compounds present in the nutmeg and mace available in Tellicherry and Kannur area. The study also revealed the importance of the area of cultivation. Due to the medicinal importance the study is very much interesting.

Keywords : Nutmeg, mace, *Myristica fragrans* Houtt., area of cultivation, chemical composition.

Introduction

Nutmeg tree is a spreading evergreen tree belonging to the small primitive family, Myristicaceae and is cultivated in Kerala, Tamil Nadu and some other states of India. It is unique among the spice plants as it produces two separate and distinct products – the nutmeg the kernel of the seed and the mace¹⁻⁷. Nutmeg seed is widely used as an aromatic spice in dishes and food products besides as an essential ingredient in many ayurvedic drugs. Its use in traditional medicine as stimulant, carminative, astringent and aphrodisiac is well known. Nutmeg is considered to be an amphrodisiac and used in tonics and electuaries. It also forms a constituent of preparation prescribed for dysentery, stomach ache, malaria, rheumatism and sciatica etc. Nutmeg oil is said to be useful in the treatment of inflammation of bladder and urinary tract.

Chemical composition and quality of nutmeg grown in major producing areas of the world have been reported to be varying widely. The variation in chemical composition may be due to the geographic, climatic and maturity conditions. A chemical evaluation of this tree spice grown in Kerala has been made by Gopalakrishnan³. The chemical composition of nutmeg found in Malabar area was not studied in detail. In this paper our studies on the nutmeg and mace available in Tellicherry and Kannur area are described.

Results and discussion

Chemical compositions of nutmeg and mace obtained from Tellicherry and Kannur area of North Malabar were determined to find out the quality and quantity of the spice.

Carbohydrate, starch, reducing sugars, protein phenol, fat and fatty acids and minerals were determined. The Tables 1 and 2 shows the exact amount of these

Table 1. Estimation of chemical components in nutmeg and mace samples from Tellicherry and Kannur areas

	Nutmeg (%)	Mace (%)
Carbohydrate	32.4 (28.5)	45.7 (47.8)
Starch	28.2 (18.10)	38.1 (26.43)
Reducing sugars	0.19 (0.10)	0.31 (0.16)
Protein	8.3 (7.5)	6.1 (6.5)
Phenol	2.8	0.5
Fat	33.8	26.4
Fatty acid composition :		
Lauric acid	8.00	1.31
Myristic acid	55.10	8.11
Palmitic acid	14.87	52.26
Stearic acid	7.3	7.98
Unidentified components	2.52	-
Bracket - Reported value ⁶ .		

Table 2. Estimation of minerals in nutmeg and mace from samples from Tellicherry and Kannur area

	Nutmeg	Mace
K (%)	0.62	0.88
Ca (%)	0.12 (120 mg)	0.11 (180 mg)
Fe (ppm)	98 (4.6 mg)	111 (12.6 mg)
Cu (ppm)	13	21.3
Zn (ppm)	16	15
Mn (ppm)	41	23
P (ppm)	150 (140 mg)	112 (100 mg)
Major essential oil constituents :		
	Nutmeg (%)	Mace (%)
Essential oil	8.70	15.80
α -Pinene	9.30	10.00
Sabinene	37.10	19.70
Safrole	4.80	3.30
Myristicin	12.50	22.00
Elemicin	27.20	30.20

components present in the nutmeg and mace. It is then compared with the components already determined from other parts of the country.

Myristicin or methoxy safrole, an antioxidant is the major aromatic constituent of nutmeg and mace oils. Studies conducted at various laboratories indicated that it has the property of scavenging cancer causing free radicals.

Saponification value is found to be very high (185.27) and it is clear that free fatty acids are present in it. The low iodine value obtained (63.5) shows few unsaturated compounds present in it. Details are given in Table 1.

The studies revealed that the nutmeg and mace obtained in the north Malabar area are comparable in quality and quantity with minor variations to that from other areas. Even though nutmeg is largely used by natives; widespread utilization is not yet made. The detailed studies are yet to be conducted. No other seed has such importance as natural medicine than the nutmeg.

Materials and methods :

Nutmeg and mace collected from Tellicherry and Kannur area were powdered separately and the oil was extracted from it. Two types of extractions were carried out. One is hot extraction and the other is cold extraction. Hot extraction was carried out by Soxhlet using petroleum ether as solvent. The extracted oil was analysed by gas chromatography. The oils obtained by hot extraction and cold extraction were analysed separately. The iodine value and saponification value of nutmeg oil were

also calculated. The various constituents were determined as follows :

Carbohydrates : Phenol sulphuric acid method for total carbohydrate – Nutmeg and mace were homogenised in alcohol. To the dried residue, water and perchloric acid were added and centrifuged. The amount of carbohydrate present in the supernatant was estimated by phenol-sulphuric acid method⁸.

Starch by anthrone reagent : Starch is an important polysaccharide. It is the storage form of carbohydrate in plants abundantly found in roots, tubers, stems, fruits and cereals. Starch are hydrolysed into simple sugars by dilute acids and the quantity of simple sugars can be measured colorimetrically⁸. Starch from nutmeg and mace was estimated from the alcoholic extract.

Reducing sugars (Nelson-Somogyi method) : Estimation of reducing sugars in nutmeg and mace samples were carried out from the alcoholic extract by Nelson-Somogyi method⁸.

Protein : Protein was estimated from nutmeg and mace by the Kjeldhal's method as described by Sadasivan and Manickam⁸.

Total free amino acid estimation : Total free amino acids in nutmeg and mace samples were estimated by the Ninhydrin method of Yapinlee and Takahashi⁹.

Phenols : The alcohol extract of nutmeg and mace samples were used for the estimation of phenol by Folin-Ciocaltease reagent⁸.

Estimation of fat : Fat from a known quantity of the seed was extracted with petroleum ether. The solvent was then evaporated off completely, dried, weighed and the percentage of fat calculated⁸.

Estimation of fatty acids : Fatty acids present in nutmeg and mace were extracted by incubating in NaOH-methanol at 70 °C for 2 h. Free fatty acids were converted to fatty acid methyl esters for GLC analysis by incubating in methanol-HCl¹⁰.

GLC of fatty acids : Methyl esters of fatty acids from fat were separated in a Perkin-Elmer Autosystem gas chromatograph equipped with PE Nelson 1022 GC plus integrator. The detector used was FID, temperature was 300 °C and that of the injection port was 200 °C. The column used was carbowax 20 M. The column oven tem-

Note

perature was programmed at 80–190 °C @ 24 °C/min with initial holding time of 1 min. On reaching 190 °C, it ran isothermally. Identification of the compound was done by comparing with Retention Time of authentic standards.

Minerals : Minerals present in nutmeg and mace were estimated by dry ashing¹¹ was carried out usually at an ignition temperature of 550 to 600 °C followed by its extraction in dilute HCl or H₂SO₄ for determining various elements.

Phosphorus was estimated by taking 30–50 mg of samples in a volumetric flask. 10 ml of vanadate-molybdate solution was added followed by 50 ml distilled water (Tandon)¹¹.

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